

X-ROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D6.3

Comparison of the X-Rotor and existing wind turbine LCoE

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://X-Rotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

The objective of this deliverable is to compare costs between the X-Rotor Concept (XRC) and standard Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWT) to determine the areas and the extent to which the XRC can provide cost of energy savings. Following on from Deliverable 6.2: “Modelled LCoE for the X-Rotor”, this report will use updated CAPEX figures from the most recent project outputs for the XRC to prepare final LCoE estimates. It will then employ the same LCoE calculation methodology to determine estimates for 3 standard horizontal axis turbine concepts: a direct drive (DD) with permanent magnet generator (PMSG); a 3-stage geared High Speed turbine with PMSG; and a 2-stage geared Medium Speed turbine with PMSG. The deliverable will consider a common farm scenario for each HAWT configuration: 100 x 5MW turbines, commissioned in 2030 with a 30-year project lifetime at a hypothetical North Sea site, 40 km from shore.

Section 2 will provide an overview of D6.2 LCoE estimates for the XRC; the updated CAPEX cost estimates; and the final XRC LCoE range that will be used as the benchmark with existing turbine configurations. Section 3 will outline the three standard turbine configurations including the inputs and methods used for the LCoE calculation. Section 4 will present the LCoE results based on Section 3 scenarios and provide a comparison of these with the XRC, highlighting the key potential cost savings. Section 5 will conclude with a summation of the results and further studies that could be undertaken e.g. considering a floating version of the XRC and upscaling the turbine.

List of acronyms

O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LCoE	Levelised Costs of Energy
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
WT	Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbine
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
VAWT	Vertical-Axis Wind Turbine
mr	Minor Repair
Mr	Major Repair
MR	Major Replacement

1 Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to compare costs between the X-Rotor Concept (XRC) and standard Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWT) to determine the areas and the extent to which the XRC can provide cost of energy savings.

The XROTOR project is developing an innovative wind turbine design that will target cost reductions and scalability. The “X-Rotor offshore wind turbine” is a Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) /Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) hybrid. It is expected that the X-Rotor concept could reduce Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE) by 20-30% by providing a:

- 25-50% reduction in OPEX (Operations and Maintenance expenditure) through no heavy components or machinery being situated at a great height above sea-water and through general simplification of the turbine. This reduces the requirement for costly heavy lift vessels for maintenance. The design also removes failure modes around the gearbox, multi-pole generator and yaw system.
- 5-25% reduction in CAPEX (Capital expenditure) by reducing the cost of drive-trains through an easily scalable approach to power take-off that does not require a gearbox or a multi-pole generator whilst achieving comparable efficiency levels in power conversion.

Deliverable 6.2: “Modelled LCoE for the X-Rotor” provided estimates of the X-Rotor LCoE. Section 2 of this deliverable will revise the XRC LCoE considering updated turbine CAPEX estimates received from WP3, 4 and 5. The final LCoE will be used to benchmark the XRC against existing turbine configurations. Sections 3 will then employ the same tools, methodology and farm scenario to determine estimates for 3 standard horizontal axis turbine concepts: a direct drive (DD) with permanent magnet generator (PMSG); a 3 stage PMSG; and a 2 stage PMSG. Results will be presented in Section 4 and provide a comparison of these with the XRC, highlighting the key potential cost savings. Section 5 will conclude with a summation of the results and further studies that could be undertaken e.g. considering a floating version of the XRC.

2 XRC LCoE Analysis

This project employs an LCoE tool adapted by UCC from their LEANWIND financial model (Devoy McAuliffe, et al., 2018) (Judge, et al., 2019). The tool and LCoE methodology are presented in D6.2. The calculation will consider turbine CAPEX costs estimated by WP4 and WP5. The University of Strathclyde have used their O&M model in WP6 to determine the energy production and maintenance costs, contributing to the overall OPEX estimate.

Following sensitivity analysis undertaken in D6.2, the baseline farm scenario for the XRC is 100 x 5MW fixed-bottomed turbines, commissioned in 2030¹ with a 30-year lifetime at a hypothetical North Sea site, 40km from shore. A generic monopile is considered across all analysis based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) and scaled in costs for a 5MW turbine. Financial assumptions include a WACC-based discount rate of 3.22% (pre-tax), a 4% debt interest rate and a loan period of 18 years. These assumptions will also be applied to the standard HAWT scenarios for comparison.

The XRC LCoE estimate is €47.39, from D6.2; however, further work has now been undertaken in WP4 and 5 to verify the XRC CAPEX costs. With these new figures, the LCoE estimate has been updated to €46.80 with a range of €42.22-49.65/MWh. This range was determined by varying the financial assumptions, considering these are very uncertain and project-specific factors that can

¹ CAPEX, OPEX and power production adjusted to assume improvements from 2021 figures to 2030 as per methodology in (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) and detailed in D6.2.

significantly impacts the LCoE. A number of financial scenarios were applied with the lowest and highest results presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Financial sensitivity analysis

Scenario	WACC	Loan Period	CTV cost	CAPEX variation	LCoE
Baseline	3.22%	18	€4,000	0%	46.42
Lowest	2.54%	12	€3,000	20% reduction in blade costs & reduction of 5% in total CAPEX across the concept	42.22
Highest	3.80%	24	€4,000	+5%	49.95
Average					45.94

Results were validated by placing them in the context of the current literature as follows:

- The NREL LCoE estimate (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) for a 600MW fixed offshore wind reference farm using 8MW turbines, commissioned in 2030.
- The BEIS report estimate (Department of Business, 2020) for 1GW farm using 12MW turbines commissioned in 2030.

This is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 5MW X-Rotor – 2030 – LCoE estimated range.

The XRC LCoE average (€45.94/MWh) and highest (€49.65/MWh) estimates are close to/within the NREL and BEIS LCoE “validation range” (€46.41-54.42/MWh), indicating that results are reasonable. It is expected that the BEIS report LCoE is significantly higher than the XRC and NREL estimates. This is because the BEIS report applies a higher discount rate based on an Internal Rate of Return (IRR) rather than WACC. Further explanation of this is provided in D6.2. While an IRR discount rate will inevitably result in a higher LCoE, it is useful to consider the BEIS estimate as the higher end of the LCoE range for a 2030 fixed Offshore Wind Farm cost estimate. It is also expected that the average XRC LCoE is close to the NREL estimate, given the majority of case study costs and financial assumptions were based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022). The lowest XRC LCoE (€42.22/MWh) is below the “validation range” suggesting either the assumptions are too optimistic, or the XRC has significant cost reduction potential. The next step is to determine where and the extent to which the XRC can provide savings. This will be done by applying the same scenario and assumptions, calculation methods and models to 3 traditional HAWTs with direct drive and geared (2 and 3 stage) drive train configurations.

3 Standard Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWT)

3.1 CAPEX

This section outlines the 3 standard HAWTs with different drivetrain configurations, which will be used for comparison with the XRC:

1. Direct drive
2. Geared Medium Speed (MS) – 2-stage
3. Geared High Speed (HS) – 3-stage

All use a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) versus a Double Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) as these are the preferred choice for most offshore wind turbines due to their reliability and performance. (Carroll, et al., 2017) provides an illustration of the key components of these 3 configurations as per Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Drive train configurations (Carroll, et al., Availability, operation and maintenance costs of offshore wind turbines with different drive train configurations, 2017)

The key differentiating features between the 3 drivetrains are:

- The Direct Drive has no gearbox, with reduced failures but a larger generator with a higher failure rate than geared generators.
- The Geared MS (2-stage) is expected to have a cheaper gearbox with a lower failure rate than the Geared HS (3-stage), but a more expensive generator with a higher number of failures.

Based on the above differentiating features, CAPEX costs for the 3 HAWTs were estimated using (BVG Associates, 2019) and scaled based on the percentage cost differences suggested in (Carroll, et al., Availability, operation and maintenance costs of offshore wind turbines with different drive train configurations, 2017) and re-produced in Figure 3.2. Here it indicates that the Geared HS will

have the highest gearbox cost, with the Geared MS at 70.5% of that cost. The Direct Drive will have the most expensive generator, followed by the Geared MS at 50% of the cost and the Geared HS at 18%. In addition, a Direct Drive turbine is also expected to have larger, heavier blades, increasing the overall rotor cost. A comparison of the Geared (medium speed) DTU 10MW reference turbine and the Direct Drive IEA 10W reference turbine indicate that there may be an increase in the blade mass by 12% for the Direct drive IEA turbine (Bortolotti, et al., 2019). Therefore, a 12% cost increase was applied to the DD HAWT blades.

Table 3.1 CAPEX comparison

	XRC	DD	GMS	GHS
Rotor	2,127,677	1,227,280	1,136,800	1,136,800
<i>Blades</i>	<i>1,912,634</i>	<i>844,480</i>	<i>754,000</i>	<i>754,000</i>
<i>Hub</i>	<i>87,000</i>	<i>87,000</i>	<i>87,000</i>	<i>87,000</i>
<i>Pitch System</i>	<i>38,280</i>	<i>58,000</i>	<i>58,000</i>	<i>58,000</i>
<i>Low Speed Shaft</i>	<i>13,203</i>	<i>23,200</i>	<i>23,200</i>	<i>23,200</i>
<i>Spinner</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>11,600</i>	<i>11,600</i>	<i>11,600</i>
<i>Blade Bearing</i>	<i>76,560</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>
<i>Fabricated steel & structural fasteners</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>87,000</i>	<i>87,000</i>	<i>87,000</i>
Tower	506,228	388,600	388,600	388,600
Nacelle	956,231	2,482,400	2,188,630	1,939,520
<i>Bedplate</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>
<i>Main bearing</i>	<i>300,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>
<i>Main shaft</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>	<i>116,000</i>
<i>Gearbox</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>286,230</i>	<i>406,000</i>
<i>Generator</i>	<i>102,431</i>	<i>1,160,000</i>	<i>580,000</i>	<i>211,120</i>
<i>Power Converter</i>	<i>408,800</i>	<i>406,000</i>	<i>406,000</i>	<i>406,000</i>
<i>Control system</i>	<i>145,000</i>	<i>145,000</i>	<i>145,000</i>	<i>145,000</i>
<i>Yaw system & bearing</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>139,200</i>	<i>139,200</i>	<i>139,200</i>
<i>Nacelle auxiliary system & cover</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>98,600</i>	<i>98,600</i>	<i>98,600</i>
<i>Small engineering components & structural fasteners</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>185,600</i>	<i>185,600</i>	<i>185,600</i>
Secondary rotors	11,322	n/a	n/a	n/a
Additional costs^c	1,972,000	1,972,000	1,972,000	1,972,000
Total (€)	5,573,458	6,070,280	5,686,030	5,436,920
Total (€/kW)	1,115	1,214	1,137	1,087

Figure 3.2 Normalized capital costs showing components from 4 drive train types (Carroll, et al., Availability, operation and maintenance costs of offshore wind turbines with different drive train configurations, 2017)

Overall, the XRC is 8% cheaper than the DD HAWT and 2% cheaper than the MS Geared HAWT but is still more expensive (3%) than the HS Geared HAWT. The main cost driver for the XRC is the blades. However, it should be considered that cost savings of over 20% are expected once the blades are optimised for a 5MW design. The current blade dimensions are more suited to a 6MW turbine. The MS Geared HAWT is more expensive than the HS Geared HAWT due to the more expensive generator, despite the cheaper gearbox. However, the latter may prove more reliable. This will be examined in section 3.2.

3.2 Power production and OPEX

The NREL 5MW reference turbine (Jonkman, Butterfield, Musial, & Scott, 2009) power curve is used for all 3 configurations. The same operational farm scenario (100 x 5MW turbines (500MW capacity), 40km from shore, commissioned in 2030) outlined for the XRC in section 2 was reviewed for the HAWTs using the University of Strathclyde O&M tool. The O&M strategy for the XRC baseline scenario is outlined in D6.2. The following summarises the baseline strategy applied to the traditional HAWTs:

- The hypothetical wind farm has 5 Crew Transfer Vessels (CTV), and a pool of 30 technicians.
- Minor repairs are assigned to CTVs and are addressed offshore.
- Jack-Up Vessels (JUV) are hired on a fix-on-fail basis for major component replacements. JUV charter durations are 60 days long.

Table 3.2 outlines the vessel costs, day rates and mobilisation costs applied in the scenarios. The failure rates are taken from the figures presented in [5]. Note that these are not calculated directly from field data, but rather derived using a reliability enhancement methodology and modelling technique involving transforming data from onshore turbines. This means that there is a considerable measure of uncertainty in the figures. SOVs are not included in the maintenance strategy, meaning that replacements of major components are all undertaken using JUVs.

Table 3.2 Vessels

Vessel	€
CTV day rate	4,000
JUV mob cost	800,000
JUV day rate	200,000

The O&M tool estimates variable O&M costs and energy production considering downtime due to failures. However, since the model focuses on the turbine, additional maintenance costs for the BoS (e.g. substructure, electrical etc.) have been added. These were calculated as 34% of the total maintenance costs for the baseline scenario based on the breakdown in (BVG Associates, 2019).² An annual fixed O&M cost of €13.65million is also included in the final OPEX based on (Stehly & Duffy, 2022). This accounts for fixed operations expenditure such as office rental space and insurance.

Table 3.3 presents the variable annual OPEX costs and annual energy production modelled for the 3 different HAWT configurations. This suggests that the direct drive has the highest reliability, resulting in the lowest OPEX and highest production while the Geared HS (3-stage) has the lowest reliability with the highest OPEX and lowest production.

Table 3.3 Standard HAWTs – OPEX and Energy production

Concept	Annual variable OPEX (€)	Annual energy production (MWh)
Direct Drive	29.7million	2,304,184
Geared - MS - 2 stage	38.5million	2,297,528
Geared - HS - 3 stage	41.9million	2,290,304

3.3 LCoE

Using the power production, OPEX and CAPEX costs outlined above, the X-Rotor project LCoE tool modelled the LCoE for each configuration, using the same financial assumptions as the XRC and outlined in section 2 above and Table 4.1 below.

4 HAWT LCoE Analysis and XRC comparison

This section provides a full comparison of the XRC with the 3 configurations of traditional HAWTs. Results from the CAPEX, OPEX and LCoE modelling outlined in Section 3 are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 XRC and traditional HAWT comparison³

		X-Rotor	Direct Drivetrain	Geared MS - 2 stage	Geared HS - 3 stage
Farm capacity (MW)	MW	500	500	500	500
Commissioning date	year	2030	2030	2030	2030
Turbine rating (MW)	MW	5	5	5	5
Turbine number	number	100	100	100	100
Project lifetime (years)	years	30	30	30	30
Distance from shore	km	40	40	40	40
Discount Rate	%	3.2%	3.2%	3.2%	3.2%
DR method	text	pre-tax real WACC	pre-tax real WACC	pre-tax real WACC	pre-tax real WACC
Development and project management	€/kW	69	69	69	69
Turbine	€/kW	931	1014	950	908
Electrical infrastructure	€/kW	527	527	527	527

² This figure remains fixed for future sensitivity analysis.

³ CAPEX, OPEX and power production adjusted to assume improvements from 2021 figures to 2030 as per methodology in (Stehly & Duffy, 2022) and detailed in D6.2.

Substructure and foundation	€/kW	377	377	377	377
Contingency, construction finance, insurance during construction	€/kW	419	419	419	419
Assembly and installation	€/kW	310	310	310	310
Lease price	€/kW	135	135	135	135
Plant commissioning	€/kW	26	26	26	26
Decommissioning	€/kW	106	106	106	106
Total CAPEX	€/kW	2,900	2,983	2,919	2,878
Annual O&M - fixed	€/kW/yr	16	16	16	16
Annual O&M - variable	€/kW/yr	39	47	61	67
Total OPEX	€/kW/yr	55	63	77	83
Energy production	MWh/ MW/yr	5,312	5,265	5,250	5,233
Capacity factor	%	60.6%	60.1%	59.9%	59.7%
LCoE	€/MWh	46.80	50.71	54.68	56.16
LCoE Range	€/MWh	42.22-49.65	46.30-53.82	50.34-57.42	52.13-59.56

Currently the XRC turbine CAPEX is 8% less than the Direct Drive HAWT, and 2% less than the Geared MS HAWT but, is 3% higher than the Geared HS HAWT. The primary advantage of the XRC is found in the lower variable OPEX at 17%; 36% and 42% less than the conventional HAWT configurations with a reduction in the overall OPEX of 12%, 28% and 33%. The XRC results in a slightly higher capacity factor and energy production of 1%, 1% and 2% respectively. The XRC LCoE is 8%, 14% and 17% lower than the Direct Drive, Geared MS and Geared HS conventional HAWTs respectively.

As outlined in section 2, there are significant uncertainties in the inputs including the financial assumptions, vessel costs and CAPEX. In particular, the current XRC design is over-engineered for a 5MW turbine and is closer to a 6MW turbine. It is expected that further optimisation would produce a 20% reduction in the blade costs. Applying this reduction results in the XRC being cheaper than all 3 HAWTs with turbine CAPEX savings of between 5-14% (1-5% total CAPEX reduction) as illustrated in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 CAPEX comparison

	XRC -baseline	XRC – 20% blade reduction	Direct Drivetrain	Geared MS – 2 stage	Geared HS – 2 stage
Turbine CAPEX (€/kW)	931	867	1014	950	908
Total CAPEX (€/kW)	2,900	2,837	2,983	2,919	2,878

Given the uncertainties in the inputs outlined above, it was determined that a range of LCoE results is more appropriate than a single estimate. Applying the same variations, Figure 4.1 presents the range of LCoE estimates for the XRC and the HAWT configurations.

Figure 4.1 Range of LCoE results

As outlined in Table 4.3, the XRC LCoE proves to be:

- 8-9% less than the Direct Drive HAWT
- 14-16% less than the Geared MS HAWT
- 17-19% less than the Geared HS HAWT

Table 4.3 LCoE Comparison

	XRC	Direct Drivetrain	Geared MS - 2 stage	Geared HS - 3 stage
High	49.65	53.82	57.42	59.56
Average	46.16	50.06	53.88	55.84
Low	42.22	46.30	50.34	52.13

Table 4.4 considers results against the original goals outlined in Section 1.

Table 4.4 Goal versus Results

	Savings Goal	Result
Turbine CAPEX	5-25%	5-14%
Variable OPEX	25-50%	17-42%
LCOE	20-30%	8-19%

As illustrated above, the XRC does have considerable cost saving potential, particularly in terms of OPEX costs and with a 8-19% reduction in LCoE. However, while close, it has not yet achieved all the expected goals (20-30% LCoE reduction) and further optimisation is both needed and possible. In particular, design improvements that would increase the CAPEX cost savings. As highlighted in this report, the current LCoE savings are expected to reduce further as the concept is further refined specifically for a 5MW turbine. Additionally, further cost savings, not covered in this report, such as manufacturing savings from easier to manufacture non-twisted blades, may well push the XROTOR LCOE cost savings higher than what is shown in this report. Earlier work where over 20% LCoE savings was achieved included comparisons with DFIG HAWT configurations which have shown high OPEX offshore driving up the overall LCoE.

5 Conclusion

Based on this analysis with current inputs from the XROTOR work packages the XRC has potential to reduce the LCoE compared to traditional turbines by 8%-19%, depending on the HAWT configuration to which it is compared.

Main cost savings of the XRC:

- Lower capital costs since there is no gearbox, no need for a bespoke generator, not twist the in blades. Based on the analysis in this report, this has resulted in turbine CAPEX savings of 5-14%
- Lower O&M costs and increased reliability due to
 - o the removal of gearbox failures, reduction in generator replacement failure rate
 - o PTO redundancy allowing partial operation with one secondary rotor;
 - o Reduced weight of nacelle and lower height of key components almost removes the need for expensive heavy lift vessels for repair and maintenance. The strategy modelled in this report uses Service Operations Vessels (SOVs) rather than Jack-up vessels (JUVs) to replace the generator and the main bearings.

The above provided savings of between 17-42% in the OPEX.

Future potential savings:

- Further cost reductions could be found through additional optimisation of the design and removing the over engineering from the X-Rotor rotor.
- Improved O&M strategy. It may be useful to consider whether further onshore maintenance for the secondary HAWT module would reduce costs and/or improve availability. These would need to be modular to facilitate this strategy. (Flannigan, Carrol, & Leithead, 2022)
- In addition, the XRC may provide considerable savings when up-scaled to larger turbines compared to traditional HAWT configurations. This is because it avoids or reduces some of the upscaling issues for HAWTs e.g. size and mass of the drive-train at hub height and gravitational blade loads (Leithead, Camciuc, Kazemi, & Carroll, 2019). The XRC can be up-scaled more cost efficiently than HAWTs. However, the design of >5MW XRC is beyond the scope of this project.
- The XRC is also particularly well-suited to floating offshore usage due to its low centre of mass, (Leithead, Camciuc, Kazemi, & Carroll, 2019) and reduced need for heavy machinery at height for maintenance. Therefore, the XRC offers additional LCoE savings potential for floating wind. However, the technical analysis of a floating XRC is beyond the scope of this project.
- The XRC has greater high density wind farm potential and low wind speed site potential due to improved wake recirculation compared to traditional HAWTs, this will lead to further LCoE savings at certain sites. The potential LCoE advantages related to the improved wake recirculation are not included in the cost analysis in this report.

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